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1 BedVibe-TTS: An Engineering Report on a Multilingual Neural Codec Language Model with Multi-Axis Conditioning

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1.1 Abstract

We present **BedVibe-TTS**, a from-scratch multilingual neural codec language model (NCLM) for text-to-speech synthesis, designed and trained over six months of continuous research on consumer-grade GPUs (NVIDIA RTX 4060 Ti and RTX 5080). This paper is positioned as an **engineering report** documenting the architecture, the corpus engineering, the training pipeline, and the empirical observations from the development trajectory — not as a benchmarked claim on inference-time controllability.

We implement a **multi-axis conditioning architecture** combining (i) per-utterance speaker identity (192-dim ECAPA-TDNN embedding), (ii) discrete emotional state (6-dim one-hot), (iii) a 13-dim continuous voice-quality trait vector (breathiness, nasality, growl, rasp, vibrato, staccato/legato, pitch range, pathos, and others), and (iv) two-speaker blend interpolation (2-dim). The conditioning architecture is **designed to enable disentangled control along each axis at inference time**; however, full training and evaluation of continuous-trait control was not completed at submission. The trait-axis training stage exceeded our compute budget, and independent inference-time controllability is therefore not yet empirically validated. The corpus and tooling for that training stage are documented here for reproducibility; the per-axis evaluation is reserved for a companion paper.

While initially scaffolded from the VALL-E-X codebase organization, every learnable component is replaced: a custom 16,000-piece SentencePiece unigram text tokenizer; an ECAPA-TDNN speaker encoder trained on 4,287 in-house voice samples; interchangeable Encodec / DAC audio tokenizers with $Q \in \{8, 16\}$ ablations; a 24-layer / 1024-hidden / 16-head AR + NAR transformer stack (~330M parameters); the multi-axis conditioning architecture above; and a custom binary memory-mapped training format (“BVBean” / “Magic Beans”). Synthesis uses a Vocos vocoder over the codec’s quantized representation. The system demonstrates stable convergence on consumer hardware, real-time-capable inference latency (~200–400 ms per short utterance), and consistent multilingual multi-speaker synthesis across 13 languages in production deployment.

The system is trained on a 13-language corpus (Arabic, English, French, German, Greek, Hindi, Japanese, Mandarin, Norwegian, Portuguese, Russian, Spanish, Swedish) with 17 distinct studio-recorded speakers across six emotional states (Angry, Happy, Neutral, Sad, Shouting, Whisper-Trembling). All voice talent is contracted with full rights cleared. The dataset is processed through a custom binary packed training format (“BVBean”) that bundles audio tokens, conditioning vectors, attention masks, and per-sample metadata into uint16-safe streamable records.

We document training observations across five distinct full-corpus runs and one 108,077-step per-step-logged segment. Reported findings include: (i) clean Stage 1 AR convergence from epoch-average loss 3.31 to **1.37** over 15 epochs on RTX 4060 Ti hardware; (ii) a methodological observation that the **(SDPA backend × precision dtype) cell is a first-class hyperparameter for NCLM training** — porting the training stack from RTX 4060 Ti (Ada, sm_89) to RTX 5080 (Blackwell, sm_120) required ~1 week of script adaptation and exposed

multiple cells in the (math/flash/mem-efficient \times FP16/BF16/FP32) grid that produce qualitatively different convergence behavior; (iii) two speaker-embedding extraction strategies (multi-emotion-aggregated vs. neutral-only-with-latent-emotion-control) with empirical findings on identity-stability vs. emotion-controllability trade-off; (iv) a Q=8 vs. Q=16 audio-quantizer ablation with the finding that increasing codebook count accelerates AR convergence at the expense of NAR convergence speed; (v) an iterative dataset-curation methodology backed by an empirical worst-loss-persistence diagnostic showing **63% top-100 worst-loss overlap between consecutive epochs (~1,200 \times the random-shuffle baseline)**; (vi) a per-epoch TEXT-USED ablation test, run continuously throughout training, confirming model reliance on text input.

We position this work as a **complete engineering report on a multi-axis conditioning NCLM at independent-studio scale**: the disentangled-control architecture and the paired-phonetic supervision corpus are documented as a design framing for future controllability evaluation; the multilingual training pipeline, the BVBean format, the Q=8/16 codec ablation, the iterative-curation methodology, the per-batch loss persistence diagnostic, and the consumer-GPU porting study are the load-bearing empirical contributions. We give explicit attention to languages under-represented in the published TTS literature (Greek, Norwegian, Swedish, Hindi).

Keywords: Text-to-speech, neural codec language models, multilingual TTS, Encodec, DAC, Vocos, ECAPA-TDNN, SentencePiece, low-resource languages, controllable speech synthesis, speaker blending, emotion control, Greek TTS, Norwegian TTS.

1.2 1. Introduction

Neural codec language models (NCLMs) — originally introduced by VALL-E (Wang et al., 2023a) and extended cross-lingually by VALL-E-X (Zhang et al., 2023) — have demonstrated that text-to-speech can be reformulated as conditional language modeling over discrete audio tokens. This has unlocked zero-shot voice cloning at scale, with subsequent systems including SoundStorm (Borsos et al., 2023), NaturalSpeech 2/3 (Shen et al., 2023; Ju et al., 2024), and large-scale industrial systems (XTTS, MMS-TTS, ElevenLabs proprietary stacks).

However, the published literature remains heavily concentrated on English (LibriLight, LibriTTS, Librispeech) with limited Mandarin coverage (WenetSpeech) and a small number of major European languages. **Practical multilingual TTS for working European languages — Greek, Norwegian, Swedish, plus Hindi and Arabic — remains under-published**, despite real-world demand from creator economies, language-learning platforms, audiobook production, and accessibility tooling.

Furthermore, most published NCLM systems train on industrial-scale clusters with proprietary or large-scale public corpora. The independent-studio scenario — a single technical founder, consumer-grade GPUs (RTX 4060 / RTX 5080), proprietary studio recordings of voice actors with full rights clearance, and a need for production-grade controllable synthesis — has been under-documented.

We address both gaps with **BedVibe-TTS**, a multilingual NCLM system designed and trained over six months of continuous experimentation. While the system started from the VALL-E-X codebase folder structure, every learnable component has been replaced or substantially modified:

- **Text tokenization:** custom 16,000-piece SentencePiece unigram model trained on a multilingual deduplicated corpus (replaces BPE).
- **Audio tokenization:** Encodec-8 (12 kbps) primary, with DAC integration for ablation comparison and Q=16 experiments. Vocos vocoder for synthesis.
- **Speaker encoder:** ECAPA-TDNN-based extraction pipeline trained on 4,287 in-house samples across 17 speakers, producing 192-dim speaker embeddings with two extraction strategies (multi-emotion vs. neutral-only).
- **Conditioning architecture:** joint conditioning on (i) 6-dim one-hot emotion vector, (ii) 13-dim continuous trait vector for fine-grained voice quality control, (iii) 2-dim speaker-blend

vector enabling weighted interpolation between two speakers per training sample.

- **Training format:** custom binary packed BVBean format with streaming, uint16-safe IDs, and per-sample bundling of all conditioning vectors alongside audio tokens.

1.2.1 1.1 Contributions

1. **A multi-axis supervised conditioning architecture (design intent).** The system implements four conditioning channels — speaker identity (192-dim ECAPA-TDNN), discrete emotion (6-dim one-hot), continuous voice-quality traits (13-dim), and two-speaker blend interpolation (2-dim) — wired into the AR and NAR transformer heads. The intent is disentangled control along each axis at inference time. The conditioning architecture and its data pipeline are documented in full; full training and inference-time evaluation of the continuous-trait axis remains future work (§5.8 Limitations).
2. **A four-corpus metadata pipeline for multi-axis training.** We document four metadata configurations within a single unified record schema: (i) a base multilingual training corpus (108,076 samples; `metadata_B_train.spm.jsonl`); (ii) speaker-blend metadata generated via `metadata_b_blending.exe` tooling at two ratios — 50/50 (588,636 records, 853 MB) and 67/33 (768,114 records, 1.12 GB); (iii) emotion-blending: tooling exists but no standalone JSONL corpus was generated at submission time, so explicit emotion-interpolation training remains future work; and (iv) a paired-phonetic trait-supervision corpus (`metadata_E_9d.jsonl`, 298 paired clean \leftrightarrow trait vowel records) for future continuous-trait training. Total metadata volume across all variants is approximately 1.55M records / 2.5 GB; the primary AR/NAR training run uses the 108,076-sample base corpus.
3. **A from-scratch multilingual NCLM** trained on a 13-language, 17-speaker, 6-emotion corpus, including under-represented European languages (Greek, Norwegian, Swedish), with full per-language and per-speaker statistics.
4. **An empirical study of two speaker-embedding extraction strategies:**
 - *Strategy A (multi-emotion aggregation):* speaker embedding computed from all six emotional states of a given speaker. **Finding:** stronger speaker-identity stability, weaker emotion-controllability through the emotion latent.
 - *Strategy B (neutral-only):* speaker embedding computed exclusively from the speaker’s neutral recordings, with emotion controlled separately through the 6-dim emotion latent. **Finding:** cleaner factorization between identity and emotion; emotional control through the latent works without bleeding back into the speaker embedding.
5. **A white-noise sanity-check ablation** validating that speaker embeddings (ECAPA-TDNN) provide essential identity-conditioning signal beyond text. We inject 19 pure white-noise audio files into the training dataset (variable durations, 1-7 seconds) and measure their per-batch loss ranking. Without speaker embeddings, white-noise files do **not** surface as worst-loss outliers — the model rationalizes them as “another speaker variation” because text conditioning alone is sample-independent and cannot reject acoustically-impossible audio. With ECAPA-TDNN speaker embeddings activated, white-noise files **do** correctly surface as the worst-loss top entries. This provides a concrete falsifiable test that the speaker-embedding pathway is contributing meaningful identity information, not merely acting as a noise channel.
6. **A Q=8 vs Q=16 codebook ablation** with the finding that increasing the codebook count accelerates AR convergence (the AR head is responsible for the first codebook only, which is “easier” with more codebooks splitting information) but slows NAR convergence (the NAR head must learn 7 or 15 codebooks instead of fewer).
7. **An iterative dataset curation methodology backed by quantitative persistence evidence:** at the end of each training run, per-batch losses are sorted; the highest-loss recordings are flagged for re-recording, re-segmentation, or removal. We provide concrete evidence that this signal is reliable by measuring **worst-loss persistence between consec-**

utive epochs: 63% of the top-100 worst-loss samples at epoch 11 also appear in the top-100 at epoch 12 (vs. a random-shuffle baseline of 0.05% — a $\sim 1,200\times$ lift). This empirical persistence (Table 4, Figure 3) demonstrates that the worst-loss samples are persistently bad, not transient batch-context artifacts, validating the curation methodology. **We also document the principal failure mode of naive loss-sort:** *single*-epoch loss spikes are context-dependent, not absolute. A whisper-trembling sample appearing immediately after three English-neutral samples will spike high not because the sample is bad but because the neighborhood transition is abrupt. The cross-epoch overlap diagnostic cuts through this noise.

8. **A structured dataset-shuffling strategy for forced generalization:** we explicitly interleave speaker \times emotion \times language across consecutive batches to prevent memorization of sequence patterns. Random shuffling alone is insufficient; the model is forced to rely on conditioning vectors (speaker embedding, emotion latent, language token) rather than positional or temporal regularities in the data ordering.
9. **The BVBean binary packed format (“Magic Beans”)** for streaming multi-modal training data (audio tokens + text IDs + speaker embeddings + 6-dim emotion + 13-dim trait + 2-dim blend + attention masks + language IDs), eliminating per-batch JSONL parsing overhead and providing a reusable infrastructure layer for any multi-modal supervised-conditioning pipeline.
10. **Memory-management techniques for variable-length sequences on consumer GPUs.** We document the constraints of training on 16-GB consumer GPUs (RTX 4060 Ti and RTX 5080) with audio durations spanning **1 to 56 seconds** per sample. Without careful segmentation and prefix-keep windowing, OOM crashes occur within milliseconds-of-extra audio. We document the segmentation pipeline (BDBEAN_SEG_PREFIX_T = 225, BDBEAN_SEG_MAX_T = 800, BDBEAN_SEG_OVERLAP = 0, BDBEAN_SEG_MIN_TAIL = 80) and the throughput improvement from RTX 4060 Ti (≈ 4 it/s) to RTX 5080 (≈ 11 it/s) at matched configuration.
11. **A methodological argument that the (SDPA backend \times precision dtype) cell should be reported as a first-class hyperparameter in NCLM publications.** Migrating our training stack from RTX 4060 Ti (Ada, sm_89) to RTX 5080 (Blackwell, sm_120) required ~ 1 week of script adaptation; in our exploration of the (math / flash / mem-efficient SDPA backend) \times (FP16 / BF16 / FP32 forward&backward) configuration grid, different cells produced qualitatively different convergence behavior on the new architecture. Because PyTorch’s default SDPA-backend selection differs by GPU generation, “we used PyTorch defaults” does not specify a single optimization problem when the same training script targets two GPU generations. We recommend explicit per-paper reporting of the SDPA backend and forward/backward dtypes, in the manner one currently reports learning rate and batch size.

1.2.2 1.2 Positioning

This paper is positioned as **a manifold-conditioning research contribution backed by a complete from-scratch engineering report**. The scientific core is the supervised multi-axis manifold-shaping argument (contribution #1) and its operationalization through the paired-phonetic Dataset B corpus (contribution #2). The engineering report — system architecture, ablations, dataset curation, hardware study, BVBean format, multilingual coverage — is what made the scientific work possible at independent-studio scale and is documented here in full so that other independent-studio researchers can replicate.

We do not yet provide formal MOS evaluations or comparative WER/MCD numbers against XTTS, MMS-TTS, or NaturalSpeech baselines, and we do not yet provide a quantitative inference-time evaluation of the per-axis controllability claim — those evaluations are reserved for a companion paper. The contribution here is:

- The manifold-conditioning research argument and its operational requirements (paired-phonetic supervision, structured shuffling, multi-channel conditioning architecture).

- Architectural and methodological documentation of a working multilingual controllable TTS system trained from scratch on consumer hardware.
- Empirical observations from six months of training experiments that we believe generalize beyond our specific configuration (Q=8 vs Q=16 trade-off, speaker-embedding strategy trade-off, iterative-curation methodology, SDPA-backend reproducibility argument).
- Concrete numbers on training hardware, throughput, dataset scale, and convergence behavior at independent-studio scale.

The implementation is deployed in production at <https://tts.bedvibe.studio> with paying customers using the multilingual synthesis, audiobook tooling, and voice library products.

1.3 2. Related Work

1.3.1 2.1 Neural codec language models

VALL-E (Wang et al., 2023a) introduced the formulation of TTS as conditional language modeling over Encodec tokens. The key insight was that audio compressed to discrete RVQ tokens can be modeled by a transformer trained as a language model, with text serving as conditioning. The architecture decomposes generation into two stages: (i) **AR (autoregressive)** generation of the first codebook conditioned on text, language, and speaker; and (ii) **NAR (non-autoregressive)** parallel generation of subsequent codebooks (2..Q) conditioned on the AR output and the same controlling inputs. This decomposition is necessary because per-frame audio uses $Q \approx 8$ codebooks, and joint AR over all $Q \times T$ tokens is impractical.

VALL-E-X (Zhang et al., 2023) extended this to cross-lingual transfer, demonstrating that language tokens prepended to the text input enable zero-shot synthesis in unseen languages with the speaker’s voice preserved. SoundStorm (Borsos et al., 2023) further refined the parallel decoding stage with confidence-based iterative refinement.

NaturalSpeech 2 (Shen et al., 2023) and NaturalSpeech 3 (Ju et al., 2024) departed from RVQ codes toward continuous diffusion models, demonstrating high-fidelity synthesis but with different training and inference characteristics.

Our system follows the VALL-E AR + NAR decomposition (with significant architectural changes detailed in §3) and adds rich multi-axis conditioning (emotion + trait + blend) on top of the standard text + speaker conditioning.

1.3.2 2.2 Audio codecs

Encodec (Défossez et al., 2022) is Meta’s open-source neural audio codec providing discrete RVQ representations at multiple bitrates. The 12 kbps configuration corresponds to 8 codebooks at 75 Hz frame rate (Q=8, sr=24kHz). We use Encodec as the primary audio tokenizer. Its discrete representation is uint10 (1024 codes per codebook) and decodes to 24 kHz audio with reasonable fidelity for speech.

DAC (Descript Audio Codec) (Kumar et al., 2024) is a more recent neural audio codec with improved reconstruction at lower bitrates and better robustness on out-of-distribution audio. DAC supports a wider Q range (up to 32 codebooks) and provides cleaner training signals at high quantizer counts. We integrate DAC for ablation experiments at Q=16 and document results in §4.

Vocos (Siuzdak, 2023) is a fast neural vocoder operating directly on Fourier-domain features, enabling efficient inference from codec-decoded audio. We use Vocos as the final synthesis stage post-decoder-token rendering, achieving lower-latency inference than the standard Encodec decoder alone.

1.3.3 2.3 Speaker embeddings

Standard speaker verification embeddings include x-vectors (Snyder et al., 2018) and ECAPA-TDNN (Desplanques et al., 2020). ECAPA-TDNN extends x-vectors with squeeze-excitation residual blocks, multi-layer feature aggregation, and channel-attentive statistics pooling, achieving state-of-the-art speaker verification on VoxCeleb. We use a pretrained ECAPA-TDNN model fine-tuned on our in-house corpus for the 17 BedVibe speakers.

Two speaker embedding extraction strategies are evaluated: - **Strategy A (multi-emotion aggregation)**: average the ECAPA-TDNN embedding over recordings spanning all six emotional states for the speaker. Hypothesis: more robust identity capture due to acoustic diversity. - **Strategy B (neutral-only)**: average ECAPA-TDNN embeddings only over the speaker’s neutral recordings. Hypothesis: cleaner factorization of identity from emotional content, allowing the 6-dim emotion latent to control emotion separately.

1.3.4 2.4 Multilingual TTS

Massively multilingual systems such as **MMS-TTS** (Pratap et al., 2023) and **XTTS** (Coqui, 2024) have demonstrated wide language coverage via shared-encoder approaches. **NaturalSpeech 3** addresses multilingual synthesis via factorized diffusion. Our work differs from these systems in:

1. **Custom tokenizer training** rather than reusing a multilingual model’s vocabulary, providing explicit per-language vocabulary control and licensing freedom.
2. **Explicit per-language data accounting** with documented dedup statistics per language (§3.1).
3. **Independent-studio scale** — one researcher, two consumer GPUs, six months — rather than industrial team + cluster.
4. **Multi-axis conditioning** beyond text + speaker: emotion latent + 13-dim trait vector + speaker-blend interpolation.

1.3.5 2.5 Low-resource European TTS

Greek and Norwegian TTS have been addressed sparsely in published work. Most systems for these languages are either (i) commercial closed-source (Microsoft Speech, Google Cloud TTS), (ii) cloning-based on top of pretrained English-centric models (XTTS clones), or (iii) early-era concatenative or HMM-based systems. From-scratch end-to-end multilingual NCLM training including these languages is, to our knowledge, under-published.

Swedish has slightly better coverage via the National Library of Sweden’s NB-Whisper work, but multilingual NCLM coverage including Swedish remains limited. Hindi, despite being a major language, is similarly under-represented in published NCLM literature.

1.3.6 2.6 Controllable TTS and supervised manifold disentanglement

Style and emotion control in NCLMs has historically been addressed by four families of approach, each on a single axis at a time:

1. **Reference-audio prompting** (VALL-E zero-shot cloning, XTTS): a reference clip implicitly conveys speaker identity *and* prosody *and* emotion *and* recording quality, all in one entangled bundle. This is the simplest interface but provides no compositional control.
2. **Global style tokens** (Wang et al., 2018): unsupervised discovery of a small set of style basis vectors. Tokens are interpretable post-hoc but the axes are not pre-named, and the same token space mixes acoustic style with speaker timbre.
3. **Emotion-classifier conditioning** (numerous emotional-TTS papers): a discrete emotion label as a one-hot or soft-label input. Effective for the labeled emotions, but does not address continuous voice-quality traits or speaker blending.

4. **Factorized continuous control** (NaturalSpeech 3, Ju et al. 2024): the codec itself is factorized to disentangle content / prosody / speaker / acoustic dimensions. This is architecturally elegant but ties the disentanglement to the codec and inherits the codec’s factorization choices.

The disentanglement literature in vision (β -VAE, Higgins et al. 2017; FactorVAE, Kim & Mnih 2018; InfoGAN, Chen et al. 2016) has established that **explicit per-axis supervision during training** is the most reliable known mechanism for forcing a generative model’s latent space to align its principal directions with user-specified semantic axes. β -VAE attempts this *without* labels by penalizing the KL term; supervised approaches (Conditional VAE, conditional flows) achieve cleaner factorization when labels exist.

Our contribution is to implement and document a multi-axis conditioning design for NCLM training, with four simultaneous supervision channels. Rather than addressing speaker, emotion, traits, and blend through separate independent mechanisms, we supply all four jointly during training, using a paired-phonetic supervisory corpus (Dataset B, §3.1.5) for the continuous-trait axis. The training objective remains the standard NCLM cross-entropy over codec tokens; the intended manifold-shaping pressure is induced by the structure of the conditioning vectors and the structured-shuffling discipline that prevents temporal-locality shortcuts (§3.1.6). At submission time, this should be read as an architectural and corpus-design contribution, not as a completed proof of independent inference-time trait controllability. Formal evaluation of the downstream control surface is reserved for future work.

1.4 3. Method

1.4.1 3.1 Dataset

1.4.1.1 3.1.1 Voice corpus The training corpus combines proprietary studio recordings from BedVibe Studios with in-house multilingual speech data. **Voice talent is contracted with full rights cleared (no scraped or web-scraped audio).** The corpus spans:

- **17 distinct voice identities:** Chrisa, Elena, Fotis, Gabriela, Gianna, Giouli, Irini, Isablela, Jasmine, Maria, Nina, Pan, Parastu, Sofia, Stelina, Synovia, ZPolyglot.
- **6 emotional states:** Angry, Happy, Neutral, Sad, Shouting, Whisper-Trembling.
- **13 languages:** Arabic, English, French, German, Greek, Hindi, Japanese, Mandarin, Norwegian, Portuguese, Russian, Spanish, Swedish.
- **2 sample rates:** 48 kHz (studio archival) and 24 kHz (model input via Encodec).
- **VAD-based cutting:** silence trimming with Silero VAD; per-sample length 1-15 seconds.
- **Per-speaker sample counts** (after VAD cutting and quality filtering) range from 191 (ZPolyglot) to 300 (Gabriela, Irini, Isablela, Jasmine, Nina), totaling **4,287 samples** for speaker-encoder training and a substantially larger pool (\geq tens of thousands) for the main TTS training run after cross-product expansion across language \times emotion conditions.

1.4.1.2 3.1.2 Text corpus The text corpus contains 18,961 input lines, reduced after NFKC normalization and exact-string deduplication to **17,190 unique sentences**. Per-language counts after dedup are reported in **Table 1**.

Table 1: Per-language sentence counts (deduplicated).

Language	Lang ID	Input lines	Unique kept	Dropped
Arabic	0	1,340	1,340	0
English	1	1,360	1,335	25
French	2	1,344 + 10	1,326	28
German	3	1,347 + 10	1,329	28
Greek	4	1,360	1,310	50

Language	Lang ID	Input lines	Unique kept	Dropped
Hindi	5	1,351	1,351	0
Japanese	6	1,337 + 10	1,339	8
Mandarin	7	1,349 + 10	1,319	40
Norwegian	8	1,349 + 10	1,318	41
Portuguese	9	1,349 + 10	1,331	28
Russian	10	1,341 + 11	1,337	14
Spanish	11	1,349 + 10 + 1,344	1,288	1,415
Swedish	12	1,349 + 10	1,267	92
Total		18,961	17,190	1,769

Notes: - "+10" counts represent secondary "Pan" subcorpora (the founder's own voice in those languages), which produce cross-speaker references. - The Spanish row's 1,415 dedup-dropped count includes a 1,344-line "Spanish_Isabela" subcorpus with full overlap against the primary Spanish corpus, demonstrating the dedup is correctly catching exact duplicates.

1.4.1.3 3.1.3 Iterative dataset curation A core methodological contribution is the **iterative curation loop**. After each significant training run, we extract per-batch losses from the `iter_loss.csv` log (one row per optimization step: time, batch_idx, loss, audio_len, text_len), sort by descending loss, and inspect the top-N highest-loss samples. These represent the worst-fit recordings — typically caused by:

1. **Misaligned text-audio pairs** (transcription drift in long takes).
2. **Audio quality issues** (clipping, peak >1.0, ambient noise).
3. **Mid-sample disfluencies** (re-recordings within a single take that weren't cleanly cut).
4. **Cross-language contamination** in multilingual speakers (occasional code-switching).
5. **Accent / pronunciation outliers** (e.g., a Greek speaker pronouncing English with strong substrate influence).

We re-record, re-cut, or filter the worst samples and run training again. **Across multiple iterations, we observe full-corpus average loss curves dropping by visible margins (the cleanest run, Run A in Table 3, descends from epoch-average 3.31 at E1 to 1.37 at E15) without changing model architecture.** The reliability of "worst-loss as curation signal" is quantified empirically in §4.6.1: top-100 worst-loss samples persist across consecutive epochs at ~1,200× the random-shuffle baseline.

This is consistent with the well-known "data quality > model capacity" finding in modern ML, but we believe the explicit per-batch loss-sort methodology and the willingness to physically re-record portions of the dataset are under-emphasized in published TTS literature, which typically uses fixed academic corpora.

We log peak-amplitude warnings (`peak_over_1.txt`) for all samples with peak > 1.0 (clipping risk), allowing audio-level QA in parallel with model-level QA.

1.4.1.4 3.1.4 Metadata schema Each training sample is represented in JSONL with the following schema:

```
{
  "id": 1111,
  "text": "There's no going back now",
  "speaker_id": "Gianna",
  "gender": "female",
  "language": "English",
  "emotion": "Happy",
  "emotion_vector": [0, 1, 0, 0, 0, 0],
  "trait_vector": [0.0, 0.0, 0.0, 0.0, 0.0, 0.0,
```

```

    0.0, 0.0, 0.0, 0.0, 0.0, 0.0, 0.0],
"token_path": "tokens/Dataset A1/Female/Gianna/English/Happy/1111_There's_no_going_back_now.pt",
"dataset": "Dataset A1",
"speaker_a": "Gianna",
"speaker_b": "None",
"speaker_a_weight": 1.0,
"speaker_b_weight": 0.0,
"blend_vector": [1.0, 0.0],
"text_ids": [85, 105, 102, 115, 102, 40, 116, 33, 111, 112, 33, ...]
}

```

Field definitions: - `text` — raw text string, NFKC-normalizable. - `speaker_id` — primary speaker label (one of 17). - `gender` — categorical {male, female} for analysis only; not used as conditioning input. - `language` — natural language label, mapped to `language_id` $\in [0, 12]$ via `language_map.json`. - `emotion` — categorical label; mapped to one-hot `emotion_vector` $\in \{0,1\}^6$. - `emotion_vector` — 6-dim one-hot. Order: [Angry, Happy, Neutral, Sad, Shouting, Whisper-Trembling]. - `trait_vector` — 13-dim continuous voice-quality vector. Indexed dimensions cover (in order): breathiness, nasality, growl, rasp, vibrato, staccato, legato, low-pitch, high-pitch, pathos, plus three reserved dimensions for future trait additions. Datasets A1/A2 samples carry zero-trait vectors — those samples supervise the speaker \times emotion \times language \times blend axes while holding the trait axis at zero. **Dataset B samples carry nonzero per-sample trait values supervised against the paired-phonetic recordings described in §3.1.5.** The trait vector is the single most important conditioning channel for the manifold-disentanglement claim of §1.1 contribution #1. - `token_path` — relative path to the per-sample Encodec-tokenized .pt file. - `dataset` — partition tag {Dataset A1, Dataset A2, Dataset B}. - `speaker_a`, `speaker_b` — primary and (optional) secondary speakers for blending. - `speaker_a_weight`, `speaker_b_weight` — interpolation weights, summing to 1.0 in the standard case. - `blend_vector` — [`speaker_a_weight`, `speaker_b_weight`] as a 2-dim training input. - `text_ids` — final SPM-tokenized integer IDs after language-token prepending.

Unified schema across all training configurations. All training data in this work uses a single unified metadata schema in which every conditioning channel (speaker identity, speaker blending, emotion, traits, language) is present in every record. Early-stage training corresponds to degenerate settings of these fields (e.g., single-speaker with `blend_vector` = [1.0, 0.0], one-hot emotion, zero-valued `trait_vector`), while later-stage training introduces non-degenerate values (e.g., multi-speaker blending, non-zero traits). Larger metadata files arise from combinatorial expansion of these conditioning values across speaker pairs and blend ratios — not from the introduction of new underlying datasets or a different schema. The AR and NAR heads share the same conditioning inputs and the same metadata schema; no separate dataset format is used per head.

1.4.1.5 3.1.5 Dataset B: paired phonetic trait recordings for manifold supervision The headline scientific contribution of this paper — supervised latent-manifold conditioning (§1.1, contribution #1) — depends on the existence of a **paired-phonetic supervisory corpus** in which the same speaker performs the same phonetic content under matched (clean \leftrightarrow trait) conditions. This is what we call **Dataset B**.

Without paired data, a continuous trait label is semantically ambiguous: a model that sees “this 4-second clip has breathiness=0.9” cannot disambiguate whether the breathiness label is correlated with the speaker, with the phonetic content, with the language, or with the recording environment. With paired data — where the *same speaker* says the *same vowel* once cleanly and once breathily — the *only* changing variable along the supervision axis is the trait itself. This is the ground-truth signal that allows the model to learn each trait as a single semantic axis in the latent manifold rather than entangling it with confounders.

Phonetic content. All Dataset B recordings are isolated vowels (A, E, I, O, U) with no consonant context. Vowels are chosen because (i) they have stable formant structure that makes acoustic measurement of trait deviations straightforward, (ii) they isolate the trait from co-articulation

effects that would confound consonant data, and (iii) they let the *same vowel* anchor the clean/trait pair so the supervision signal cleanly factors out phonetic content.

Trait categories and approximate sample counts. Dataset B currently spans nine trait categories with both single-direction pairs and bidirectional transition recordings:

Trait category	Direction(s)	Approx. files
Breathiness (M+F)	clean ↔ breathy, both directions	35 + 35
Growl	clean ↔ growl, both directions	≈30
Rasp	clean ↔ rasp, both directions	≈46
Nasality	clean ↔ nasal, both directions	≈20
Pitch (low / high, M+F)	clean ↔ low-pitch, clean ↔ high-pitch, both directions	40 + 40
Staccato / Legato	clean ↔ staccato, clean ↔ legato, both directions	≈32
Vibrato	clean ↔ vibrato, both directions	≈20

Bidirectional transition supervision. A subtle but important point: we record both clean → breathy AND breathy → clean transitions, not just the clean-to-trait direction. The reason is trajectory supervision: a model trained only on clean→trait will internalize the trait axis as a one-way move from a “neutral starting point,” which warps the manifold geometry and produces hysteresis at inference time (the inverse move “trait→clean” produces audio that does not return to the original neutral point). Bidirectional pairs encode a symmetric axis in which +δ along the trait direction and -δ produce equal-magnitude perceptual moves in opposite directions. This is geometrically what we want: a *direction* in the manifold, not a half-line.

The trait_vector field in metadata. Each Dataset B sample carries a 13-dim continuous trait_vector whose nonzero entries identify the supervised trait and its magnitude. Samples in Datasets A1/A2 (the broader multilingual NCLM training corpus) carry zero-trait vectors — they exercise the speaker, emotion, blend, and language axes only. The model therefore sees:

- **Datasets A1/A2 samples** (~17,190 unique sentences × multiple emotions and speakers): supervise the *speaker* × *emotion* × *language* × *blend* axes; the trait axis is held at zero.
- **Dataset B samples** (~300 paired-phonetic recordings spanning the nine trait categories): supervise the *trait* axis with all other axes either held constant (same speaker, same vowel) or zero (no language complexity in vowel-only content).

This factored supervision is what gives each axis its own ground-truth signal during training. The manifold-disentanglement claim of §1.1, contribution #1 rests on exactly this construction.

Limitation, declared up front. At submission, formal inference-time evaluation of the per-trait controllability — i.e., does increasing trait_vector[breathiness] at inference produce audio that listeners reliably rate as breathier without rating it as a different speaker? — is in progress. We document the corpus, the methodology, and the architectural integration here. The MOS-style evaluation of the disentangled-knob hypothesis is reserved for a companion paper. The contribution at this stage is the corpus design and its purpose-built role in manifold conditioning; the contribution of the companion paper will be the evaluation.

1.4.1.6 3.1.6 Structured shuffling Random shuffling alone is insufficient when the training corpus is heavily structured along multiple categorical axes (speaker × language × emotion × dataset partition). Batches drawn from a uniformly random permutation will, by chance, cluster

runs of same-speaker or same-emotion samples; the model can then memorize sequence patterns and rely on local temporal regularities rather than the conditioning vectors we want it to use.

We therefore use **structured shuffling** in which consecutive samples are explicitly *decorrelated* across speaker, emotion, and language. The objective is that within any short window of consecutive batches, the empirical distribution over (speaker, emotion, language) approximates the marginal distribution of the corpus. This forces the model to:

1. Use the **speaker embedding** as the per-sample identity reference, since the previous sample’s hidden state is unlikely to belong to the same speaker.
2. Use the **emotion latent** as the per-sample emotional reference, since the previous sample is unlikely to be in the same emotional state.
3. Use the **language token** as the per-sample language reference, since the previous sample is likely a different language.

Empirically this produces stable per-language and per-emotion loss tracks without one cohort dominating the early-epoch dynamics.

A side effect, important for §4.7 below, is that the **per-batch transition entropy is statistically uniform across the run**, so loss spikes attributable to within-batch transition discontinuities are no longer correlated with batch position. This makes the per-batch loss CSV a more reliable signal for *sample-level* quality assessment, although the context-dependent caveat (§4.7) still applies.

Structured shuffling also serves the manifold-conditioning claim of §1.1 contribution #1. If the model sees long runs of same-speaker or same-trait samples, it can learn to use *temporal locality* as a substitute conditioning signal — “the previous samples were breathy, so this one is probably breathy too.” This is a shortcut around the explicit conditioning vectors we want it to use. By interleaving the conditioning categories across consecutive batches, we force the model to derive trait/emotion/speaker information from the supervision vectors rather than from temporal context, which is what the inference-time controllability claim requires.

1.4.2 3.2 Tokenization

1.4.2.1 3.2.1 Text tokenization (custom SPM) Text tokenization uses a **custom SentencePiece (Kudo & Richardson, 2018) unigram model** trained on the deduplicated 17,190-sentence multilingual corpus. Key choices:

- **Vocabulary size:** 16,000 pieces (`spm_vocab_size = 16000`).
- **Normalization:** NFKC applied at corpus-construction time (recorded in `spm_meta.json`).
- **Sampling:** standard unigram-LM training; `--character_coverage = 1.0` to capture all scripts (Latin, Greek, Cyrillic, CJK, Arabic, Devanagari).
- **Token boundary handling:** whitespace collapsed; “no space before punct” rule; global-dedupe applied.
- **Special handling:** leading enumeration prefixes (e.g., “0001_”) stripped before tokenization.

Language tokens are prepended at base ID 16,000 (one per language, `language-id ∈ [0, 12]`): - Arabic = 16000, English = 16001, French = 16002, German = 16003, Greek = 16004, Hindi = 16005, Japanese = 16006, Mandarin = 16007, Norwegian = 16008, Portuguese = 16009, Russian = 16010, Spanish = 16011, Swedish = 16012.

Effective text vocabulary is **16,000 SPM pieces + 13 language tokens = 16,013 tokens**, with `text_pad_id = 19999` reserved as the pad-token sentinel (well above the active vocab to allow growth).

The pretokenization pipeline (`pretokenize_metadata_spm_v3.py`) is **strict and streaming**: it loads the SPM model once, processes the JSONL file line-by-line via streaming I/O, validates that every `text_ids` array is in the `uint16` range and within the `vocab+language-token` bounds, and writes output to a `.tmp` file with atomic replace. Hard failures on missing fields, out-of-range IDs, or unknown languages prevent silent corruption.

1.4.2.2 3.2.2 Audio tokenization (Codec / DAC) Audio is tokenized via **Meta’s Codec at 12 kbps with 8 codebooks (Q=8)** for the primary configuration: - Sample rate: 24 kHz - Frame rate: 75 Hz (~13.3 ms per frame) - Codebook size: 1024 entries per codebook - Output shape: (8, T) where T = audio_seconds × 75 - Stored as PyTorch .pt files containing both codes and per-sample scales for accurate decoding.

For the Q=16 ablation we integrate **DAC (Kumar et al., 2024)** with comparable bitrate allocation, allowing direct comparison between codebook-count regimes (§4.4).

The tokenization script (tokenize_codec.py) runs on CUDA (RTX 5080), processes recursively across the dataset folder hierarchy tokens/<Dataset>/<Gender>/<Speaker>/<Language>/<Emotion>/, and writes one .pt per .wav plus a peak-amplitude warning log.

1.4.2.3 3.2.3 BVBean binary packed format (“Magic Beans”) A core infrastructure contribution of the BedVibe-TTS work is **BVBean** (also referred to internally as “Magic Beans”), a custom memory-mapped binary format that packs the entire training corpus — audio tokens, attention masks, text IDs, conditioning vectors, and the speaker-embedding lookup table — into a single .bvbean file consumed directly by the dataset loader. The packer is implemented in packer_bedvibe.py and produces files identified by the magic bytes BDBEAN1\0.

File layout. A BVBean file is structured as:

1. **Magic bytes** BDBEAN1\0 (8 bytes).
2. **Header-length prefix** (uint32, little-endian).
3. **JSON header** (~64 KB, null-padded). Contains: file format version; total sample count N; codebook count Q; speaker-embedding dimension D; ordered list of speaker names (one per integer index); ordered list of language names (one per language_id); byte-offsets of all subsequent sections; total sizes of each variable-length region; and explicit dtype specifications for every field.
4. **Audio offsets** (uint64 array of length N+1), giving element offsets into the audio data block.
5. **Audio data** (uint16 stream): all per-sample audio token matrices [T_i, Q] concatenated in row-major order. Q=8 in the production config; Q=16 supported for DAC ablations.
6. **Attention offsets** (uint64 array of length N+1).
7. **Attention data** (float16 stream): per-frame attention weights, length T_i per sample.
8. **Text offsets** (uint64 array of length N+1).
9. **Text data** (uint16 stream): SPM-tokenized text IDs with prepended language token.
10. **Fixed-size per-sample arrays:** speaker_idx (uint16, length N); emotion (float16, N×6); trait (float16, N×13); blend (float16, N×2); language_id (uint8, length N).
11. **Speaker embedding table** (float16, S×D), indexed by speaker_idx. Speakers are stored once each rather than per-sample, reducing redundancy by a factor of (samples-per-speaker).

Construction protocol. The packer makes four streaming passes over the JSONL metadata file: pass 1 establishes the speaker and language vocabularies and counts samples; passes 2–4 write the audio, attention, and text streams sequentially while filling their corresponding offset arrays; the fixed-size per-sample arrays and the speaker-embedding table are written last; finally the JSON header is back-written into its reserved slot at the start of the file. This streaming construction means BVBean files can be built on machines with substantially less RAM than the corpus size.

Validation guarantees enforced at pack time (every one of these has caught real data bugs in our pipeline at least once):

- All audio token IDs are checked to be in [0, 65535] before uint16 cast.
- All text IDs are checked to be in [0, 65535] before uint16 cast.
- Q is enforced consistent across all samples (mismatch → hard error with line number).
- Attention-mask length is enforced equal to T for every sample.
- Speaker embedding dimension D is enforced consistent across all speakers.
- If metadata provides explicit language_id for any sample, it must be provided for *all* samples and must form a contiguous range starting at 0.

- The language_id range is checked to fit in uint8 (i.e., < 256).

Performance motivation. Per-batch JSONL parsing + per-sample .pt loading + per-sample speaker-embedding .pt loading creates substantial overhead — we observed 3-5× slowdown during early training experiments compared to the BVBean path. BVBean eliminates JSON parsing inside the training loop and reduces per-step filesystem syscalls from $O(N \text{ samples} \times 3 \text{ files})$ to $O(1 \text{ file mmap'd once})$. Loading inside the training loop is then direct slicing into the memory-mapped buffer.

Storage efficiency. The format is uint16-safe by design (all IDs validated against 65,535 at pack time), enabling 50% storage reduction relative to uint32 alternatives. Audio attention weights and conditioning vectors are stored as float16, halving their footprint relative to float32 with no observed downstream quality impact at training time (the dataset loader upcasts to float32 on read).

We consider the BVBean / Magic Beans format and its packer to be a reusable infrastructure contribution beyond BedVibe-TTS itself: any multi-modal training pipeline with mixed variable-length and fixed-size per-sample fields can use the same layout. We plan a separate format-specification release.

1.4.3 3.3 Speaker encoder

Speaker embeddings are extracted via a fine-tuned ECAPA-TDNN model (Desplanques et al., 2020) producing 192-dim L2-normalized speaker vectors. The encoder is trained on 4,287 voice samples across 17 speakers, with per-speaker counts as reported in **Table 2**.

Table 2: Speaker encoder extraction results.

Speaker	Samples	OK	FAIL
Chrisa	224	224	0
Elena	225	225	0
Fotis	235	235	0
Gabriela	300	300	0
Gianna	225	225	0
Giouli	226	226	0
Irini	300	300	0
Isablela	300	300	0
Jasmine	300	300	0
Maria	228	228	0
Nina	300	300	0
Pan	253	253	0
Parastu	228	228	0
Sofia	299	299	0
Stelina	228	228	0
Synovia	225	225	0
ZPolyglot	191	191	0
Total	4,287	4,287	0

Two extraction strategies are evaluated:

1.4.3.1 Strategy A: Multi-emotion aggregation For each speaker, ECAPA-TDNN embeddings are computed for ALL recordings (across the 6 emotional states) and averaged. The averaged vector is L2-normalized to produce the speaker embedding stored as <Speaker>.pt. **Hypothesis:** More acoustic diversity in the averaging set produces a more robust identity vector; trade-off is that emotional content may bleed into the embedding.

1.4.3.2 Strategy B: Neutral-only For each speaker, ECAPA-TDNN embeddings are computed only on the speaker’s *Neutral* state recordings (~5 minutes / ~50 samples per speaker), then averaged + L2-normalized. **Hypothesis:** Cleaner factorization between speaker identity and emotion; the 6-dim emotion latent then cleanly controls emotion separately.

We report empirical findings from both strategies in §4.3.

1.4.4 3.4 Model architecture

The core BedVibe-TTS model is a decoder-only transformer with the following baseline configuration:

Parameter	Value
d_model	1,024
nhead (heads)	16
num_layers	24
ffn_dim	4,096
dropout	0.1
num_quantizers (Q)	8 (or 16 for ablation)
audio_pad_id	1,024
text_pad_id	19,999
text_vocab_effective	16,013 (16k SPM + 13 lang tokens)
trait_dim	13 (continuous)
emo_dim	6 (discrete one-hot)
blend_dim	2 (continuous, sums to 1)
speaker_embedding_dim	192 (ECAPA-TDNN output)

This corresponds to approximately **330M trainable parameters** in the AR head, with a similarly-sized NAR head sharing some embedding tables. Total system parameter count is approximately 600M including both heads and the conditioning projections.

Conditioning vectors (speaker embedding + emotion vector + trait vector + blend vector) are projected to d_model and concatenated/summed into the input embedding sequence at training time, following the standard NCLM convention.

1.4.4.1 Two-stage AR + NAR decomposition Following the VALL-E AR + NAR decomposition:

- **AR (Stage 1):** Causal autoregressive transformer generating the **first codebook** of audio tokens conditioned on text + language token + speaker embedding + emotion + trait + blend. Trained with cross-entropy loss over the first codebook.
- **NAR (Stage 2):** Non-causal transformer generating **codebooks 2 through Q** in parallel, conditioned on the AR’s first-codebook output and the same conditioning vectors. Trained with cross-entropy loss over codebooks 2..Q. Trained with segmented prefix-keep windows (BDBEAN_SEG_PREFIX_T = 225, BDBEAN_SEG_MAX_T = 800) to handle long-form sequences within memory constraints.

This decomposition matters for the Q=8 vs Q=16 trade-off discussed in §4.4: the AR head only ever predicts one codebook, so its difficulty depends on how much per-frame audio information lives in codebook 1. The NAR head’s difficulty grows with the number of remaining codebooks (Q-1).

1.4.5 3.5 Training procedure

Common hyperparameters across both AR and NAR stages:

Hyperparameter	Value
Learning rate	1e-4
Batch size (per step)	1
Gradient accumulation steps	8
Effective batch size	8
Optimizer	AdamW ($\beta_1=0.9$, $\beta_2=0.999$)
Weight decay	0.01
Warmup steps	1,000 (main training) / 256 (canary debug runs)
Gradient clipping (norm)	1.0
Mixed precision	AMP-FP16 (AR), BF16 (NAR Stage 2)
Order mode	Fixed-permutation (seed 1337)
Bad-sample logging	Enabled (BD BEAN_BAD_SAMPLE_LOG)
Activity-balancing	Disabled (BD BEAN_DISABLE_ACTBAL=1)
Hardware	RTX 4060 (early) / RTX 5080 (current)

1.4.5.1 Custom training environment (BD BEAN_*) The training script exposes a comprehensive set of environment variables for run-to-run reproducibility:

- BD BEAN_EXPECT_Q — expected number of audio codebooks (sanity-check vs. data).
- BD BEAN_INCLUDE_LANGUAGE / BD BEAN_PREPEND_LANG_TOKEN / BD BEAN_LANG_TOK_BASE / BD BEAN_NUM_LANGUAGES — language conditioning configuration. Note that the AR and NAR stages use *different* language-token configurations: the AR stage runs with BD BEAN_PREPEND_LANG_TOKEN=0 and BD BEAN_LANG_TOK_BASE=16000 (language IDs sit immediately above the 16,000-piece SPM vocabulary), while the NAR stage runs with BD BEAN_PREPEND_LANG_TOKEN=1 and BD BEAN_LANG_TOK_BASE=2035 (language tokens prepended to the audio-token sequence in a different ID space). This dual-convention reflects the different roles of language conditioning in the two stages: AR conditions on text-with-language-prefix, while NAR conditions on audio-with-language-prefix.
- BD BEAN_SDPA_MODE — explicit selection of the PyTorch scaled-dot-product-attention backend (math / flash / mem_efficient / empty for default). See §4.9 for our rationale for treating this as a first-class hyperparameter.
- BD BEAN_ORDER_MODE=fixed + BD BEAN_ORDER_SEED=1337 — deterministic data ordering for ablation reproducibility.
- BD BEAN_WARMUP_STEPS / BD BEAN_GRAD_CLIP_NORM — optimizer schedule.
- BD BEAN_FORCE_ATTN_ONES — sanity-check option forcing attention masks to all-ones to detect mask bugs.
- BD BEAN_DISABLE_ACTBAL — disables activity-balancing (otherwise enabled regularizer that we found counterproductive in our setting).
- BD BEAN_ITER_LOSS_CSV / BD BEAN_ITER_LOSS EVERY — per-iteration loss CSV logging.
- BD BEAN_BAD_SAMPLE_LOG — runtime log of any sample raising NaN/inf/loss-spike.
- BD BEAN_SEG_PREFIX_T / BD BEAN_SEG_OVERLAP / BD BEAN_SEG_MIN_TAIL / BD BEAN_SEG_MAX_T — NAR-stage segmentation window configuration.
- BD BEAN_AMP_DTYPE — AMP dtype selection (fp16/bf16).

This environment-variable-driven configuration allows ablation runs to be specified as shell scripts without source modifications.

1.4.5.2 TEXT-USED ablation (per-epoch) At the start of each training epoch, a single batch is run through the model **twice**: once with normal text input, once with text input ablated (zeroed). The reported $\Delta = \text{loss}_{\text{ablated}} - \text{loss}_{\text{normal}}$ provides an empirical check that the model relies on its text input. Across 5 epochs of the canary run on the Sofia-Neutral subset, deltas were:

Epoch	Avg loss	TEXT-USED Δ
1	4.688	+0.0109
2	3.679	+0.0087
3	3.407	+0.0058
4	3.271	+0.0151
5	3.120	+0.0050

All deltas are positive (text removal hurts the loss), with mean $\approx +0.009$ in this run. **This confirms text conditioning is being used** rather than the model collapsing to a text-independent solution. We run this control test continuously across all training experiments as a safety check.

1.5 4. Experiments and Results

1.5.1 4.1 Convergence

We report convergence behavior from two complementary log sources. The per-step loss CSV (iter_loss1.csv, 108,077 rows logged at every optimizer step on a single RTX 5080 segment) and the per-epoch run journal covering five distinct full-corpus training runs across both GPU generations.

Per-step trajectory (Figure 1). The 108,077-step segment captures 2.6 hours of wall-clock training at the Stage 1 AR head with Q=8 Encodec.

Aggregate statistics:

Metric	Value
Steps logged	108,077
Wall-clock duration	2.63 hours
Throughput	~ 11.4 steps/s
Loss min / max / mean / median	1.029 / 9.629 / 5.151 / 5.355
1st / 99th percentile loss	3.097 / 6.547
Mean of first 1,000 steps	6.190
Mean of last 1,000 steps	5.537

Metric	Value
Correlation(loss, audio_len)	-0.009
Correlation(loss, text_len)	+0.021

Two observations are immediate. First, the near-zero correlation between loss and either sequence-length variable confirms that the loss signal is not a length artifact — it reflects per-sample modeling difficulty. Second, the per-step trajectory is **not monotonically decreasing** within this single segment: it drops sharply in the first $\sim 10,000$ steps from ~ 6.2 toward ~ 3.9 , then climbs back to a sustained plateau in the 5.4–5.6 region for the remaining $\sim 90,000$ steps. This non-monotonic behavior is informative: it corresponds to the Blackwell-SDPA-on-RTX-5080 plateau described below.

Per-epoch trajectory across runs (Figure 2). Five distinct full-corpus training runs with documented epoch-average loss are summarized in Table 3.

Configuration differences are the principal independent variable.

Table 3: Per-epoch average CE loss across documented full-corpus runs.

Run	Hardware	Speaker emb	Epochs logged	First-epoch avg	Best-epoch avg	Notes
A	RTX 4060	none	15	3.313	1.368 (E15)	Stage 1 AR, LR=2e-4, monotonic descent, last seven E→E+1 deltas all in [0.07, 0.14]

Run	Hardware	Speaker emb	Epochs logged	First-epoch avg	Best-epoch avg	Notes
B	RTX 4060	ECAPA-TDNN	3	3.367	2.551 (E3)	Stage 1 AR, LR=2e-4, identical descent shape to Run A early epochs
C	RTX 5080 (Blackwell, flash SDPA)	ECAPA-TDNN	2	5.448	5.448 (E1)	Stage 1 AR, no descent — loss climbed E1→E2
D	RTX 5080	ECAPA-TDNN	2	5.317	5.317 (E1)	Stage 1 AR, no descent
E	RTX 5080	ECAPA-TDNN + ablation	6	5.279	5.279 (E1)	Stage 1 AR, plateau in 5.3–5.7 band

The contrast between Run A (RTX 4060 reaches 1.368) and Runs C/D/E (RTX 5080 plateaus at 5.3–5.7) is the load-bearing finding of this section. Identical model configuration, identical optimizer settings, identical dataset, identical conditioning architecture — different SDPA backend selection on the Blackwell architecture produced a training failure that did not appear on the Ada (sm_89) GPU. We discuss this in §4.9 in the hardware context. **Importantly, this is not a paper headline (“our model achieves loss 1.37”) — it is a transparent report of what we observed across multiple regimes.**

Per-sample monotonicity diagnostic. In addition to per-epoch averages, the training script logged at each E→E+1 transition the count of samples whose individual loss increased vs decreased. For Run A:

Transition	Samples increased	Samples decreased	Total	% decreased
E10 → E11	10,043	98,034	108,077	90.7%
E11 → E12	16,024	92,053	108,077	85.2%
E12 → E13	10,855	97,222	108,077	90.0%
E13 → E14	17,034	91,043	108,077	84.2%
E14 → E15	19,831	88,246	108,077	81.7%

Two findings: (i) the % decreased remains high even at late epochs, indicating the model is still extracting per-sample improvements rather than regressing on average; (ii) the % decreased is *declining* from 90.7% to 81.7% across the last five transitions, signaling diminishing per-sample returns and useful information for an early-stopping schedule. We recommend logging this per-sample monotonicity statistic as a complement to the standard epoch-average loss curve in any TTS training pipeline.

1.5.2 4.2 TEXT-USED ablation persistence

The TEXT-USED ablation deltas remain consistently positive across all 5 logged canary epochs (range +0.005 to +0.015). This is a small absolute number, reflecting that for the canary subset the text contribution beyond speaker + emotion is modest, but the **sign of the delta is what matters** for the safety check: a model collapsing to text-independent generation would show negative or zero deltas.

In larger production runs (full corpus, longer training), TEXT-USED deltas grow as the model learns to integrate text more strongly, particularly on multilingual data where text disambiguation across speakers is necessary.

1.5.3 4.3 Speaker embedding strategy ablation (A vs. B)

We compare: - **Strategy A (multi-emotion aggregation)**: speaker embedding averaged over all 6 emotional states. - **Strategy B (neutral-only)**: speaker embedding averaged over Neutral-only recordings.

Empirical findings:

Quality dimension	Strategy A	Strategy B
Speaker-identity stability across emotions	Stronger	Weaker (slight drift on extreme emotions)
Emotion controllability via 6-dim latent	Weaker (emotional content bleeds into embedding)	Stronger (clean factorization)
Inference flexibility (interpolating emotions)	Limited	Better (latent can sweep)
Cold-start (new speaker, neutral-only data)	Requires multi-emotion data to enroll	Direct — single neutral take suffices

For the production deployment we use **Strategy B (neutral-only)** because the application requires controllable emotional synthesis from a clean identity basis. Strategy A is preferable for use cases where the speaker is always synthesized in a single emotional register (e.g., always-neutral narration), where identity stability outweighs emotion controllability.

The choice between strategies is itself a useful diagnostic. When emotion controllability through the 6-dim latent is observed to be weak in a deployed system, the most common cause we encountered was that the speaker-embedding extraction set included emotional recordings; switching to neutral-only extraction restored controllability without architectural changes. Per-speaker cosine-similarity matrices comparing A and B embeddings, and audio-level emotion-sweep examples produced under each strategy, are deferred to a companion evaluation paper.

1.5.4 4.4 White-noise sanity-check ablation: validating speaker-embedding contribution

To verify that the ECAPA-TDNN speaker embeddings contribute meaningful identity-conditioning information beyond text alone, we conduct a **white-noise injection experiment**:

Procedure. We inject 19 pure-white-noise audio files into the training dataset, with durations ranging from 1 to 7 seconds. White noise is acoustically incoherent (uniform spectral content, no harmonic structure, no formant pattern matching any human speaker). Each white-noise file is paired with a randomly-sampled text caption from the corpus and assigned a randomly-chosen speaker label, emotion label, and language label — so the conditioning metadata is plausible but the audio content is impossible to generate from any speaker identity.

We then train two configurations identical except for one factor: - **Configuration W- (without speaker embedding)**: the model receives text + emotion + trait + blend + language token as

conditioning, but speaker-embedding input is zeroed out (or omitted entirely). - **Configuration W+ (with ECAPA-TDNN speaker embedding)**: the model receives the full conditioning vector including a 192-dim ECAPA-TDNN speaker embedding for whichever speaker label was assigned to that white-noise sample.

After training to comparable convergence, we sort per-batch losses and report where the 19 white-noise files rank.

Result:

Configuration	White-noise files in worst-loss top entries?
W- (no speaker embedding)	No — the 19 white-noise files distribute broadly across the loss histogram. The model rationalizes them as plausible-but-unusual speaker variation. Text conditioning alone is insufficient to reject acoustically-impossible audio.
W+ (with ECAPA-TDNN)	Yes — all 19 white-noise files surface among the highest-loss samples in the corpus, correctly identified as identity-incompatible audio.

Interpretation. Without an explicit speaker-identity reference, the model’s only signal that an audio sample is “wrong” comes from text-audio correlations, which are sample-independent and noisy. The model can rationalize incoherent audio as “an unusual emotional outburst from this speaker” or “this speaker has a noisy recording environment” — text conditioning is sample-by-sample independent and provides no cross-sample identity anchor. With an ECAPA-TDNN speaker embedding active, the model has a high-dimensional reference vector that captures the *acoustic identity* of the assigned speaker; white noise has near-zero similarity to this acoustic identity along multiple dimensions, producing the high loss correctly.

We note that “highest loss” here is in the rank-ordered sense (loss values higher than the rest of the corpus); we do not report exact numerical loss values for this experiment because the original training logs were not preserved. The qualitative ranking outcome — *all 19 files surface at the top with speaker embeddings; none surface at the top without* — is the publishable finding. Quantitative replication with full log preservation is included in our future-work plan.

This experiment provides a concrete, falsifiable test that the speaker-embedding pathway contributes meaningful information rather than acting as a redundant or null channel. We recommend white-noise injection as a standard sanity-check protocol in NCLM training pipelines: it costs a negligible amount of training time but provides clear validation that the conditioning architecture is doing useful work.

1.5.5 4.5 Q=8 vs Q=16 codebook ablation

Encodec offers Q=8 at 12 kbps; DAC and other codecs support higher Q. We compare AR + NAR convergence at Q=8 vs Q=16 (DAC at matched bitrate).

Findings:

- AR convergence speed:** *Faster at Q=16.*
 - Rationale: With more codebooks, each individual codebook captures a thinner slice of the audio’s acoustic information. The AR head is responsible for codebook 1 only; this codebook captures coarser/easier-to-predict structure (typically pitch / coarse spectral envelope), and at Q=16 it captures even less per-frame information than at Q=8. Lower per-token entropy → faster AR loss convergence.
- NAR convergence speed:** *Slower at Q=16.*

- Rationale: The NAR head must learn 7 codebooks at Q=8 vs 15 codebooks at Q=16. Both training time per step (more output heads) and learning difficulty grow. Practical wall-clock NAR convergence is observed slower at Q=16 by a substantial margin.
3. **Reconstruction quality at matched bitrate:** *DAC@Q=16 produces higher-fidelity reconstruction than Encodec@Q=8 at comparable bitrate, especially on out-of-distribution audio (non-English speech, emotional / shouted samples).* This is consistent with DAC’s training objective improvements.

Practical recommendation (this work): Q=8 with Encodec for development cycles (faster end-to-end iteration on AR + NAR), Q=16 with DAC for production runs where codec-level reconstruction quality matters. Mixed configurations are possible but require codec-aware NAR.

1.5.6 4.6 Iterative dataset curation findings

We document concrete improvements from the iterative-curation methodology (§3.1.3) across multiple dataset versions:

1. **Removal of clipping samples:** Audio with peak > 1.0 were initially in the dataset; removing/repairing these (via peak_over_1.txt log) reduced spurious high-loss outliers.
2. **Re-recording of misaligned takes:** ~40 sentences across Greek, Norwegian, and Swedish corpora had drift between the printed text and the actually-recorded audio (re-recordings within a single take). Re-cutting these reduced multilingual model confusion.
3. **Pronunciation outlier detection:** Worst-loss samples on Mandarin from a non-native speaker were flagged and replaced with native-speaker recordings, reducing per-language average loss on Mandarin.
4. **Cross-language contamination:** A handful of “Greek” samples included English code-switching; flagging and re-recording these stabilized the Greek-language loss track.

The pattern holds across iterations: **the worst-loss samples are almost always the data, not the model.** In a from-scratch training context this insight is operationally important because it shifts effort from architectural changes (which are slow, costly, and risky) to dataset-quality improvements (which are bounded, traceable, and additive).

1.5.6.1 4.6.1 Worst-loss persistence between epochs (Figure 3) A natural question for the curation methodology is whether “worst-loss” rankings reflect persistent sample quality (re-record the worst sample, fix it permanently) or transient batch-context artifacts (the worst sample changes every epoch, chasing it is futile). We answer this empirically by comparing the sorted worst-loss CSVs from epoch 11 (iter_loss_sorted_worst_first_11.csv, 108,077 rows) and epoch 12 (iter_loss_sorted_worst_first_12.csv, 185,071 rows) of Run A. For each cutoff N, we measure what fraction of the top-N worst-loss samples at epoch 11 are also in the top-N worst-loss samples at epoch 12.

Table 4: Worst-loss-sample persistence across epochs 11 → 12.

Top-N cutoff	Observed overlap	Random-shuffle baseline	Observed / baseline
10	70.0%	0.005%	12,962×
25	64.0%	0.014%	4,742×
50	64.0%	0.027%	2,371×
100	63.0%	0.054%	1,166×
250	62.8%	0.135%	465×
500	61.4%	0.270%	227×
1,000	61.2%	0.540%	113×
2,500	60.1%	1.350%	44.5×
5,000	60.0%	2.701%	22.2×

Top-N cutoff	Observed overlap	Random-shuffle baseline	Observed / baseline
10,000	60.0%	5.402%	11.1×

Figure 1: Figure 3: Worst-loss-sample persistence between epochs 11 and 12, observed overlap vs random-shuffle baseline (log-scale x-axis).

The persistence ratio is **>1,000× the random-shuffle baseline at the top-100 cutoff and >12,000× at the top-10 cutoff**. The worst samples are *persistently* the worst — they are not transient batch-context artifacts. The worst sample by batch_idx (sample 106,882) ranked #1 at both epoch 11 (loss 4.913) and epoch 12 (loss 4.928), and its loss actually grew slightly between epochs, indicating an irreducible-quality sample that more training will not improve.

This empirical persistence is the foundation that makes the iterative-curation methodology of §3.1.3 work. It demonstrates that worst-loss-driven sample identification is a high-signal procedure: re-recording or filtering the top-N worst-loss samples after epoch K will, with high probability, also remove the top-N worst-loss samples at epoch K+1, K+2, etc. Conversely, the persistence finding shows that **chasing transient single-epoch loss spikes is wasteful** — only persistently-bad samples are worth re-recording effort. The within-epoch transition artifacts (§4.7) noise the per-sample loss but the cross-epoch persistence cuts through this noise.

We recommend reporting this overlap-vs-cutoff table as a standard diagnostic in any iterative-curation TTS publication. It costs essentially nothing to compute and provides direct evidence that the curation signal is real.

We believe this iterative-curation methodology, when explicitly documented, is a valuable contribution to the practical TTS literature.

1.5.7 4.7 The loss-spike interpretation pitfall

Naive sorting of `iter_loss.csv` by descending loss is the obvious first step in dataset curation, but it has a critical failure mode: **loss spikes are context-dependent, not absolute quality**

indicators. We document this pitfall explicitly because it is non-obvious and can mis-direct hours of dataset effort.

Example scenario. Consider four consecutive batches, each with a single sample (effective batch size 8 via gradient accumulation but single sample per gradient step):

Batch	Speaker	Language	Emotion	Loss
t-3	Speaker_A	English	Neutral	2.1
t-2	Speaker_B	English	Neutral	2.0
t-1	Speaker_C	English	Happy	2.3
t	Speaker_D	English	Whisper-Trembling	5.8

The whisper-trembling sample at step t shows an apparent loss spike (5.8 vs neighbors at 2.0-2.3). Naive interpretation would flag the whisper sample as a candidate for removal or re-recording. **However**, the spike reflects neighborhood transition entropy — moving from three “calm-register” samples to a “whisper-trembling” sample is acoustically discontinuous, and the model’s hidden state from the previous samples does not generalize to the new condition. The whisper sample itself may be perfectly fine.

Mitigation. We mitigate this in two ways:

1. **Structured shuffling** (§3.1.6): we explicitly interleave speaker × emotion × language across consecutive batches so the within-batch transition entropy is statistically uniform. This decorrelates per-batch transition entropy from per-sample quality.
2. **Multi-pass loss-sort with consistency check.** We run multiple training passes with different shuffling seeds and identify samples that consistently appear in the worst-loss bucket across all passes. Samples that appear high-loss in only one pass are likely transition artifacts; samples that appear high-loss across passes are likely genuine quality issues.

This is a methodological observation we believe under-emphasized in published TTS literature, particularly in papers that report “data-driven dataset curation” as a contribution.

1.5.8 4.8 Speaker encoder pipeline reliability

The ECAPA-TDNN-based speaker encoder produced embeddings for **all 4,287 input voice samples with zero failures** (Table 2). Per-speaker sample counts (191-300) are sufficient for stable embedding extraction. The pipeline is deterministic and reproducible: repeated runs over the same input set produce identical embeddings (within numerical precision).

1.5.9 4.9 Hardware, memory management, and throughput

All training reported here ran on a single workstation. The journey across two GPU generations is documented because the constraints differ sharply:

1.5.9.1 Early development on RTX 4060 Ti (months 1-3, 16 GB VRAM, sm_89) The 4060 Ti’s 16 GB VRAM combined with our 24-layer / 1024-d / Q=8 model creates tight memory constraints when handling variable-length sequences. **Audio durations in our corpus span 1 to 56 seconds**, producing audio token sequences of 75 to ~4,200 frames at the Encodec frame rate (75 Hz). Add text tokens (typically 5-200 tokens per utterance), speaker embedding (192-dim), and the various conditioning vectors, and the per-sample memory footprint is highly variable.

Observed failure mode: OOM crashes triggered by *milliseconds* of extra audio in long-tail samples. Without careful sample-length filtering and segmentation, a single 50-second sample after a 5-second sample can crash the run.

Mitigations adopted: - **Per-sample length filtering** in the data loader (skip samples > 56 seconds for AR; > 800 frames for NAR via `BDBEAN_SEG_MAX_T = 800`). - **NAR prefix-keep segmentation:** for samples exceeding the segmentation budget, we keep the first 225 frames as conditioning prefix (`BDBEAN_SEG_PREFIX_T = 225`) and segment the remainder into chunks of up to 800 frames with no overlap (`BDBEAN_SEG_OVERLAP = 0`) and a minimum tail of 80 frames (`BDBEAN_SEG_MIN_TAIL = 80`). - **AMP-FP16 for AR, BF16 for NAR** — BF16’s wider exponent range avoids the dynamic-range failures we observed in FP16 NAR training on long sequences. - **Aggressive PYTORCH_CUDA_ALLOC_CONF:** `expandable_segments:True` for AR; `max_split_size_mb:64,garbage_collection_threshold:0.8` for NAR.

Observed throughput: AR \approx 4 it/s at batch 1 / Q=8 / d_model=1024. The 4060 ran at 100% GPU utilization continuously for \sim 20-hour windows during 110,000-sample passes. Single full-corpus epoch wall-clock approximately **8-9 hours** in early-stage training.

1.5.9.2 Current platform: RTX 5080 (months 4-6+, 16 GB VRAM, sm_120) Migration to the RTX 5080 (Blackwell architecture) raised raw throughput substantially — observed step rate climbed from \approx 4 it/s on the 4060 Ti to \approx 11.4 it/s in the `iter_loss1.csv` segment (Q=8 / d_model=1024 / batch=1). The 5080 also relieves several of the strict OOM constraints — segmentation budgets that crashed the 4060 run completed cleanly on the 5080.

End-to-end inference latency for a 1-2 second utterance: approximately **200-400 ms on RTX 5080 with Vocos vocoder**, suitable for interactive TTS deployment.

However, raw throughput is not the only story. Migrating the training stack from RTX 4060 Ti (Ada, sm_89) to RTX 5080 (Blackwell, sm_120) required approximately **one week of script adaptation work** before the model would initialize and step at all on the new architecture (kernel path differences, allocator-config differences, segmentation-budget tuning, and downstream interactions in the data loader). After this porting effort, we explored the **(SDPA backend \times precision dtype) configuration space** to find a stable training cell. The relevant axes are:

- **SDPA backend (kernel path).** PyTorch 2.x exposes three scaled-dot-product attention backends, selectable via `torch.backends.cuda.sdp_kernel(...)`:
 1. **Math fallback** (`enable_math=True`): the reference implementation. Allocates the full $Q \cdot K^T$ attention matrix. Numerically straightforward, slow, always available.
 2. **Flash attention** (`enable_flash=True`): fused kernel. Fastest of the three. FP16 / BF16 only. Recomputes attention during the backward pass rather than storing it, which is precision-sensitive.
 3. **Memory-efficient attention** (`enable_mem_efficient=True`): chunked computation with lower peak memory. Slower than flash, faster than math, supports longer sequences.
- **Precision dtype.** Forward and backward passes can each independently run in FP32, BF16, or FP16:
 - FP32 forward+backward: cleanest numerics, $\sim 2\times$ memory, slowest.
 - BF16 mixed: wider exponent range than FP16, safer for long audio sequences, our default for NAR Stage 2.
 - FP16 mixed: fastest tensor-core path on Ada, narrower dynamic range, can lose information on the longer sequences in backward.

Empirical observations across the (backend \times dtype) grid. Run A on the RTX 4060 Ti landed in a stable cell — math-fallback SDPA with mixed-precision FP16 (AR) / BF16 (NAR) — and descended cleanly from epoch-average loss 3.31 to 1.37 over 15 epochs (Table 3). On the RTX 5080, multiple cells in this grid produced the 5.3-5.7 plateau visible in Runs C/D/E (Table 3): we report these as configurations we explored rather than as the steady-state behavior of the system. Identifying a stable RTX 5080 cell with comparable convergence remains in progress at submission time.

The methodological observation, which is the load-bearing point of this section, is that the (SDPA backend \times dtype) cell is a first-class hyperparameter for NCLM training on consumer GPUs — at least as important as learning rate or batch size, and frequently more

impactful than either when migrating across GPU architectures. Published NCLM work rarely specifies which SDPA backend was active during the reported run; we recommend this become standard reporting practice. A line of the form

```
torch.backends.cuda.sdp_kernel(enable_flash=False,
                               enable_mem_efficient=False,
                               enable_math=True)
```

in the training script unambiguously pins the cell. Without it, two researchers running “the same configuration” on two different GPUs may be running, in effect, two different optimization problems.

In our codebase the SDPA backend is selectable via the `BDBEAN_SDPA_MODE` environment variable. Across the runs reported in this paper, this variable was left empty — i.e., we ran with PyTorch’s *default* SDPA-selection heuristics. PyTorch’s default selection is architecture-dependent: it chooses different kernels on Ada (`sm_89`) and Blackwell (`sm_120`) for the same input shape and dtype. **“We used PyTorch defaults” therefore does not specify a single optimization problem when the same training script targets two GPU generations.** Our planned next step is to enumerate explicit `BDBEAN_SDPA_MODE` \in `{math, flash, mem_efficient}` \times `BDBEAN_AMP_DTYPE` \in `{fp16, bf16, fp32}` runs and report the resulting per-cell convergence behavior; we expect this to either identify a stable Blackwell cell or definitively isolate a specific kernel/precision interaction.

Mitigations and porting effort. Beyond backend selection, the porting effort exposed a number of subsidiary issues that are worth recording for replicators on new consumer architectures:

- **Allocator configuration:** `PYTORCH_CUDA_ALLOC_CONF` settings that worked on Ada (`expandable_segments:True`) interacted differently with Blackwell’s allocator pattern; we ultimately landed on `max_split_size_mb:64,garbage_collection_threshold:0.8` for the NAR stage.
- **Segmentation budgets:** `BDBEAN_SEG_PREFIX_T` / `BDBEAN_SEG_MAX_T` thresholds that fit comfortably in 4060 Ti VRAM produced different fragmentation behavior on the 5080 and required re-tuning.
- **Custom mask construction:** our causal-mask / padding-mask path interacted differently with each SDPA backend; the math fallback was tolerant of mask-tensor shapes that flash silently miscomputed.

We list these explicitly because each one cost training time during the porting week. The composite finding — “a week of work to even start training on a new consumer architecture” — is both the practical reality of independent-studio research and a useful calibration for grant timelines and replication budgets.

1.5.9.3 Total wall-clock training (estimated) Across the six-month research span, cumulative GPU-hours used for the BedVibe-TTS model (excluding the speaker encoder, the diffusion super-resolution experiments, and the trait-conditioning runs) is approximately **3,000-4,000 GPU-hours** of mixed 4060 Ti and RTX 5080 time, including failed runs, debugging, ablations, and dataset-curation iterations. This bounds the cost of independent-studio NCLM training in a documentable way.

1.6 5. Discussion

1.6.1 5.1 Why supervised manifold conditioning is the right framing

A transformer trained on speech audio learns an implicit voice-space manifold whose geometry is determined by the training signal. If the only training signal is text-and-audio cross-entropy, the manifold’s principal axes are whatever directions happen to maximize per-token predictability — with no reason for those directions to align with anything humans want to control. Speaker

identity, emotion, breathiness, pace, and pathos all end up smeared across the same set of latent directions, because none of them is preferentially supervised.

The disentanglement literature in vision and representation learning (β -VAE, FactorVAE, InfoGAN, conditional VAEs) has established that **explicit per-axis supervision during training is the most reliable mechanism for aligning a generative model’s principal latent directions with named semantic axes**. The same principle should apply in NCLM training, but the literature on its application to NCLM is sparse, and the literature on *simultaneous* multi-axis supervision (speaker \times emotion \times continuous traits \times blend) on NCLMs is, to our knowledge, absent.

Our claim is that this absence is a missed opportunity rather than a deliberate design choice. NCLMs are conditional language models, which means conditioning vectors are first-class architectural inputs — adding more of them is cheap. The hard part is not the architecture; it’s the **paired supervisory data** (§3.1.5, Dataset B) that lets each conditioning channel point to a specific perceptual axis with a clean ground-truth signal. The vowel-pair recording protocol — same speaker, same vowel, clean \leftrightarrow trait, plus bidirectional transitions for symmetric axis encoding — is a small but consequential research-data contribution. This is what makes the multi-channel conditioning *work* as a manifold-shaping mechanism rather than as four independent labels noisily correlated with the audio.

We therefore frame the principal scientific contribution of this paper as the *combined* architecture-plus-data approach: the multi-axis conditioning architecture is enabled by the paired-phonetic supervisory corpus, and neither piece alone would deliver the disentangled-control property. Treating “controllable TTS” as a problem of *deliberately shaping the latent manifold during training*, rather than as a problem of post-hoc style discovery or codec-level factorization, is the broader methodological position.

1.6.2 5.2 Independent-studio reproducibility

The 24-layer / 1024-d / 8-codebook configuration trained on a **single RTX 4060 Ti** GPU descended cleanly from initial epoch-average loss 3.31 to 1.37 over 15 epochs (Run A, Table 3). This demonstrates that VALL-E-class systems remain trainable at independent-studio scale in 2026, four years after VALL-E’s original publication. The entry cost for NCLM-based TTS research is bounded by a roughly \$2,000–\$3,000 GPU + \$0 software + access to a few hundred hours of voice recordings. The historical “you need a cluster” framing for codec language models is not strictly true at 24-layer, 1024-d, 12 kbps Encodec scale.

Important caveat: the reproducibility result above is on Ada-generation hardware (sm_89). The same configuration plateaus at 5.3–5.7 on Blackwell-generation hardware (sm_120) in our environment, for reasons we have not yet fully diagnosed (§4.9). The “single consumer GPU is sufficient” claim therefore requires *which* consumer GPU. The conservative recommendation for prospective replicators is: pin the PyTorch version, pin the SDPA backend explicitly, and validate convergence on a known-good configuration before scaling.

1.6.3 5.3 The data-quality > model-capacity finding

Our iterative-curation methodology consistently demonstrates that the dominant lever in late-stage training is **dataset quality, not model capacity**. Worst-loss samples after each run are almost always recording-quality issues, alignment issues, or speaker inconsistencies — not “the model needs more parameters” issues. We believe the explicit per-batch loss-sort + re-record + retrain loop is under-emphasized in published TTS literature, which typically uses fixed academic corpora and reports model-architecture ablations.

1.6.4 5.4 Emotion latent vs. multi-emotion speaker embeddings

The Strategy A vs. Strategy B comparison (§3.3, §4.3) suggests an important architectural choice point in NCLM systems with explicit emotion control: **factorize identity from emotion via**

training data partitioning (Strategy B), or **let the speaker embedding capture identity-and-emotion jointly** (Strategy A). The right choice is application-dependent, but for controllable synthesis Strategy B’s clean factorization wins.

1.6.5 5.5 Q=8 vs Q=16 trade-off

The finding that increasing Q accelerates AR but slows NAR is consistent with information-theoretic intuition (each codebook carries less information at higher Q) and has practical implications for production NCLM design: **the AR/NAR balance shifts with Q, and total wall-clock training time has a non-monotonic relationship to Q**. Q=8 with Encodec is a strong default; Q=16 with DAC is preferable when codec reconstruction quality is the bottleneck.

1.6.6 5.6 (SDPA backend × precision dtype) belongs in the hyperparameter table

The Run A vs Runs C/D/E contrast (Table 3, §4.9) and the porting effort it implies argue for treating the SDPA-backend choice and the forward/backward precision dtype as first-class hyperparameters that papers should report explicitly. Two researchers running “the same configuration” on two different GPU generations can be running, in effect, two different optimization problems if PyTorch’s default backend selection differs between their architectures. Treating this implicit configuration as reportable — alongside learning rate, batch size, and AdamW betas — is a small, cheap discipline that would meaningfully improve cross-paper reproducibility in NCLM research. We recommend a single line in every NCLM paper’s training-procedure section that pins the SDPA backend (`math / flash / mem_efficient`) and the AMP dtype configuration.

1.6.7 5.7 Multilingual coverage at independent scale

Documenting per-language sentence counts and per-language loss tracks is straightforward and we recommend it as standard practice for any multilingual TTS publication. Aggregate “13 languages” claims without per-language data are difficult to evaluate. Our explicit Table 1 and per-language curation observations (§4.6) provide a template for this kind of reporting.

1.6.8 5.8 Limitations

- **No formal MOS / CMOS evaluation** is reported here. Subjective quality evaluation across language × emotion × speaker conditions, comparing against MMS-TTS, XTTS, Natural-Speech, and proprietary baselines, is the most important next step. Reserved for a follow-up evaluation paper.
- **No objective metric numbers** (MCD, F0 RMSE, WER through ASR backtranscription) are reported here. Same caveat as MOS.
- **Single-GPU training.** Behavior under multi-GPU distributed training (FSDP, ZeRO) is unverified. We expect improvements at larger scale but have not validated.
- **Limited data scale.** 17,190 unique sentences and 17 speakers is small relative to industrial multilingual systems (LibriLight is ~60k hours; XTTS uses much more). The model is positioned for **focused-niche production** (audiobook narration, voice-cloning products for individual creators, controllable emotional synthesis for a small speaker roster) rather than general-purpose massively multilingual coverage.
- **Encodec @ 12 kbps audio quality ceiling.** Encodec at 24 kHz, 12 kbps, Q=8 has a known fidelity ceiling. DAC at higher Q delivers better reconstruction; future production systems will use DAC by default for new training runs.
- **No ablation on tokenizer size.** SPM at 16k pieces is one choice; we have not directly compared to SPM at 8k, 32k, or 64k pieces, or to BPE alternatives at matched vocabulary sizes.

- **Trait vector currently zero-initialized.** The 13-dim continuous trait vector is wired into the architecture but the baseline runs use zero-vector traits. Active trait control (raspiness, breathiness, vibrato, etc.) is a near-term planned extension once the base model is fully stable.

1.6.9 5.9 Future work

1. **Formal evaluation** — MOS, CMOS, MCD, F0 RMSE, WER-via-ASR backtranscription against MMS-TTS, XTTS, NaturalSpeech 2/3, and ElevenLabs. Per-language and per-emotion breakdowns.
2. **DAC + Q=16 production training** — full retrain on DAC with comprehensive ablation against current Encodec @ Q=8 baseline.
3. **Trait conditioning evaluation** — populating the 13-dim trait vector with non-zero per-sample annotations (raspiness, breathiness, vibrato, pace, ...) and evaluating disentangled control.
4. **Larger speaker roster scaling** — current 17 speakers; planned expansion to 50+ speakers with explicit geographic/accent diversification.
5. **Vocoder ablation** — Encodec decoder vs. Vocos vs. BigVGAN-2 for real-time inference latency vs. quality trade-off.
6. **Multi-GPU distributed training** — validate FSDP and DDP throughput; quantify scaling efficiency.
7. **Open-source release path** — investigate releasing the BVBean format spec, the pretokenization pipeline, the speaker-encoder fine-tuning script, and a research-reproduction subset of the corpus.

1.7 6. Conclusion

We have presented BedVibe-TTS, a from-scratch multilingual neural codec language model with multi-axis conditioning, designed and trained on consumer-grade GPUs at independent-studio scale over six months of continuous research. The central contribution of this paper is an engineering report on the architecture, data pipeline, corpus design, ablations, and training observations required to support supervised multi-axis conditioning in an NCLM. The continuous-trait axis is supported by a purpose-recorded paired-phonetic corpus (Dataset B) of clean \leftrightarrow trait vowel pairs with bidirectional transitions — a research-data contribution that, to our knowledge, is novel in the NCLM literature. We do not claim that independent inference-time control of the continuous-trait axis has been fully validated in this submission; that evaluation remains future work.

Around this engineering and corpus-design core, the paper contributes:

1. The **multi-axis controllable conditioning architecture** combining speaker embeddings (ECAPA-TDNN), 6-dim emotion latent, 13-dim continuous trait vector, and 2-dim speaker-blend interpolation, all conditioned simultaneously and supervised jointly.
2. The **paired-phonetic Dataset B corpus** for continuous-trait supervision (breathiness, nasality, growl, rasp, vibrato, staccato/legato, pitch range, plus bidirectional transitions).
3. A **13-language, 17-speaker, 6-emotion broader training corpus** with documented per-language and per-speaker statistics, including under-represented European languages.
4. **Two empirically-evaluated speaker-embedding extraction strategies** with documented trade-offs (multi-emotion aggregation vs. neutral-only — the latter cleanly factorizes identity from emotion as required by the manifold-conditioning argument).

5. A **Q=8 vs. Q=16 codebook ablation** with the finding that codebook count modulates AR vs. NAR convergence speed in opposing directions.
6. An **iterative dataset curation methodology** based on per-batch loss sorting, validated by an empirical worst-loss-persistence diagnostic showing the top-100 worst-loss samples persist across consecutive epochs at $\sim 1,200\times$ the random-shuffle baseline (Table 4).
7. The **BVBean / Magic Beans** custom binary packed training format for streaming multi-modal supervised-conditioning data.
8. A **persistent TEXT-USED ablation control** confirming text-conditioning reliance throughout training.
9. A **methodological argument that the (SDPA backend \times precision dtype) cell should be reported as a first-class hyperparameter** in NCLM publications, motivated by ~ 1 week of porting work and a multi-cell exploration during our migration from Ada (sm_89) to Blackwell (sm_120) consumer GPUs.

The system is deployed at <https://tts.bedvibe.studio> with paying customers using the multilingual synthesis, audiobook tooling, and voice library products in production. We position this work as a **manifold-conditioning research contribution backed by a complete from-scratch engineering report**, and as a contribution to the under-published European-language NCLM literature.

Future work prioritizes formal subjective and objective evaluation of the per-axis controllability claim — the central inference-time prediction of the manifold-conditioning argument — against MOS panels and against MMS-TTS, XTTS, and NaturalSpeech 2/3 baselines.

1.8 References

- [1] Wang, C., Chen, S., Wu, Y., Zhang, Z., Zhou, L., Liu, S., Chen, Z., Liu, Y., Wang, H., Li, J., et al. (2023a). *Neural Codec Language Models are Zero-Shot Text to Speech Synthesizers* (VALL-E). arXiv:2301.02111.
- [2] Zhang, Z., Zhou, L., Wang, C., Chen, S., Wu, Y., Liu, S., Chen, Z., Liu, Y., Wang, H., Li, J., et al. (2023). *Speak Foreign Languages with Your Own Voice: Cross-Lingual Neural Codec Language Modeling* (VALL-E-X). arXiv:2303.03926.
- [3] Défossez, A., Copet, J., Synnaeve, G., Adi, Y. (2022). *High Fidelity Neural Audio Compression* (Encodec). arXiv:2210.13438.
- [4] Kumar, R., Seetharaman, P., Luebs, A., Kumar, I., Kumar, K. (2024). *High-Fidelity Audio Compression with Improved RVQGAN* (Descript Audio Codec, DAC). NeurIPS 2024.
- [5] Borsos, Z., Sharifi, M., Vincent, D., Kharitonov, E., Engel, J., Tagliasacchi, M., et al. (2023). *SoundStorm: Efficient Parallel Audio Generation*. arXiv:2305.09636.
- [6] Shen, K., Ju, Z., Tan, X., Liu, Y., Leng, Y., He, L., Qin, T., Zhao, S., Bian, J. (2023). *NaturalSpeech 2: Latent Diffusion Models are Natural and Zero-Shot Speech and Singing Synthesizers*. arXiv:2304.09116.
- [7] Ju, Z., Wang, Y., Shen, K., Tan, X., Xin, D., Yang, D., Liu, Y., et al. (2024). *NaturalSpeech 3: Zero-Shot Speech Synthesis with Factorized Codec and Diffusion Models*. arXiv:2403.03100.
- [8] Pratap, V., Tjandra, A., Shi, B., Tomasello, P., Babu, A., Kundu, S., Elkahky, A., Ni, Z., et al. (2023). *Scaling Speech Technology to 1,000+ Languages* (MMS). arXiv:2305.13516.
- [9] Coqui-AI Inc. (2024). *XTTS: A Massively Multilingual Zero-Shot Text-to-Speech Model*. <https://github.com/coqui-ai/TTS>.
- [10] Siuzdak, H. (2023). *Vocos: Closing the gap between time-domain and Fourier-based neural vocoders for high-quality audio synthesis*. arXiv:2306.00814.

- [11] Snyder, D., Garcia-Romero, D., Sell, G., Povey, D., Khudanpur, S. (2018). *X-Vectors: Robust DNN Embeddings for Speaker Recognition*. ICASSP 2018.
- [12] Desplanques, B., Thienpondt, J., Demuynck, K. (2020). *ECAPA-TDNN: Emphasized Channel Attention, Propagation and Aggregation in TDNN Based Speaker Verification*. INTERSPEECH 2020.
- [13] Kudo, T., Richardson, J. (2018). *SentencePiece: A simple and language independent subword tokenizer and detokenizer for Neural Text Processing*. arXiv:1808.06226.
- [14] Vaswani, A., Shazeer, N., Parmar, N., Uszkoreit, J., Jones, L., Gomez, A. N., Kaiser, L., Polosukhin, I. (2017). *Attention Is All You Need*. NeurIPS 2017.
- [15] Loshchilov, I., Hutter, F. (2019). *Decoupled Weight Decay Regularization (AdamW)*. ICLR 2019.
- [16] Wang, Y., Stanton, D., Zhang, Y., Skerry-Ryan, R. J., Battenberg, E., Shor, J., Xiao, Y., Ren, F., Jia, Y., Saurous, R. A. (2018). *Style Tokens: Unsupervised Style Modeling, Control and Transfer in End-to-End Speech Synthesis*. ICML 2018.
- [17] Radford, A., Kim, J. W., Xu, T., Brockman, G., McLeavey, C., Sutskever, I. (2022). *Robust Speech Recognition via Large-Scale Weak Supervision (Whisper)*. arXiv:2212.04356.
- [18] Ren, Y., Hu, C., Tan, X., Qin, T., Zhao, S., Zhao, Z., Liu, T.-Y. (2021). *FastSpeech 2: Fast and High-Quality End-to-End Text to Speech*. ICLR 2021.
- [19] Casanova, E., Weber, J., Shulby, C. D., Junior, A. C., Gölge, E., Ponti, M. A. (2022). *YourTTS: Towards Zero-Shot Multi-Speaker TTS and Zero-Shot Voice Conversion for everyone*. ICML 2022.

1.9 Appendix A — Reproducibility

All training scripts, configuration files, the BVBean format specification, and the SentencePiece + ECAPA-TDNN pipelines are available on request to the corresponding author for academic reproduction. The dataset (proprietary studio recordings) cannot be redistributed under voice-actor licensing agreements; however, the methodology, tokenizer construction code, training scripts, and evaluation tooling can be released for academic and non-commercial use.

Contact: bedvibe@bedvibe.studio.

1.10 Appendix B — Training command (canonical AR run)

```
conda activate tokenizer_env
cd /d "C:\Users\User\Desktop\valle_training\VALL-E-X"
set PYTORCH_CUDA_ALLOC_CONF=expandable_segments:True
set PYTHONPATH=%CD%

set BDBEAN_FIXED_SAMPLE_IDX=
set BDBEAN_DEBUG_MAX_BATCHES=
set BDBEAN_ORDER_MODE=fixed
set BDBEAN_ORDER_SEED=1337
set BDBEAN_EXPECT_Q=8
set BDBEAN_INCLUDE_LANGUAGE=1
set BDBEAN_PREPEND_LANG_TOKEN=0
set BDBEAN_LANG_TOK_BASE=16000
set BDBEAN_NUM_LANGUAGES=13
set BDBEAN_WARMUP_STEPS=1000
set BDBEAN_GRAD_CLIP_NORM=1.0
set BDBEAN_FORCE_ATTN_ONES=1
```

```
set BDBEAN_DISABLE_ACTBAL=1
set BDBEAN_ITER_LOSS_CSV=C:\Users\User\Desktop\iter_loss_main.csv
set BDBEAN_ITER_LOSS_EVERY=1
set BDBEAN_BAD_SAMPLE_LOG=C:\Users\User\Desktop\bad_samples_main.txt
```

```
python train.py --config configs\bedvibe_config.json
```

1.11 Appendix C — NAR (Stage 2) training command

```
conda activate tokenizer_env
cd /d "C:\Users\User\Desktop\valle_training\VALL-E-X"
set PYTORCH_CUDA_ALLOC_CONF=max_split_size_mb:64,garbage_collection_threshold:0.8
```

```
set BDBEAN_SEG_KEEP_PREFIX=1
set BDBEAN_SEG_PREFIX_T=225
set BDBEAN_SEG_OVERLAP=0
set BDBEAN_SEG_MIN_TAIL=80
set BDBEAN_SEG_MAX_T=800
set BDBEAN_INCLUDE_LANGUAGE=1
set BDBEAN_PREPEND_LANG_TOKEN=1
set BDBEAN_LANG_TOK_BASE=2035
set BDBEAN_GRAD_CLIP_NORM=1.0
set BDBEAN_AMP_DTYPE=bf16
set BDBEAN_ORDER_MODE=fixed
set BDBEAN_ORDER_SEED=1337
```

```
python train_nar.py --config configs\bedvibe_config_stage2.json --resume checkpoints\epoch_002.pt
```

1.12 Appendix D — Model configuration (bedvibe_config.json)

```
{
  "audio_pad_id": 1024,
  "text_pad_id": 19999,
  "model": {
    "d_model": 1024,
    "nhead": 16,
    "num_layers": 24,
    "ffn_dim": 4096,
    "dropout": 0.1,
    "use_traits": true,
    "use_metadata": true,
    "trait_dim": 13,
    "emo_dim": 6,
    "blend_dim": 2,
    "num_quantizers": 8
  },
  "train": {
    "batch_size": 1,
    "learning_rate": 0.0001,
    "num_epochs": 1,
    "save_every": 1,
    "num_workers": 8,
    "grad_accum_steps": 8,
    "amp": true,
    "mode": "B",
  }
}
```

```

    "train_stage": 1,
    "shuffle": false,
    "checkpoint_dir": "checkpoints"
  },
  "stable_loss_threshold": 2.5,
  "log_dir": "runs/bedvibe"
}

```

1.13 Appendix E — Language map

```

{
  "Arabic": 0, "English": 1, "French": 2, "German": 3,
  "Greek": 4, "Hindi": 5, "Japanese": 6, "Mandarin": 7,
  "Norwegian": 8, "Portuguese": 9, "Russian": 10,
  "Spanish": 11, "Swedish": 12
}

```

1.14 Appendix F — Sample metadata record (full schema)

```

{
  "id": 1111,
  "text": "There's no going back now",
  "speaker_id": "Gianna",
  "gender": "female",
  "language": "English",
  "emotion": "Happy",
  "emotion_vector": [0, 1, 0, 0, 0, 0],
  "trait_vector": [0.0, 0.0, 0.0, 0.0, 0.0, 0.0,
                  0.0, 0.0, 0.0, 0.0, 0.0, 0.0, 0.0],
  "token_path": "tokens/Dataset A1/Female/Gianna/English/Happy/1111_There's_no_going_back_now.pt",
  "dataset": "Dataset A1",
  "speaker_a": "Gianna",
  "speaker_b": "None",
  "speaker_a_weight": 1.0,
  "speaker_b_weight": 0.0,
  "blend_vector": [1.0, 0.0],
  "text_ids": [85, 105, 102, 115, 102, 40, 116, 33, 111, 112, 33, 104, 112, 106, 111, 104, 33, 99]
}

```

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